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Asociación comunitaria en la Universidad de Jazan

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Resumen

Destinado a revelar las diferencias estadísticamente significativas entre los promedios de las estimaciones de los profesores sobre la realidad de la práctica de los requisitos administrativos en términos de (planificación, organización y coordinación) para activar la asociación comunitaria en la Universidad de Jazan y las variables: género, tipo de la universidad, años de servicio. Se utilizaron los métodos descriptivos y el cuestionario con una muestra aleatoria (290) de miembros de la facultad de posición académica durante el 2do semestre (2019). Los resultados, existe acuerdo entre la muestra para practicar los requisitos administrativos relacionados con (planificación, organización y coordinación) para activar la asociación comunitaria en la Universidad de Jazan.

Palabras clave: Requisitos administrativos; Universidad de Jazan; Asociación comunitaria.

Community Partnership at Jazan University

Abstract

Aimed to reveal the statistically significant differences between the averages of the faculty members' estimates of the reality of practicing the administrative requirements in terms of (planning, organization, and coordination) to activate the community partnership at Jazan University and the variables: gender, type of college, years of service. The descriptive methods and the questionnaire with a random sample (290) of faculty members of academic position during 2nd semester (2019) were used. The Results, there is an agreement among the sample to practice the administrative requirements related to (planning, organization, and coordination) in order to activate the community partnership at Jazan University.

Keywords: Administrative requirements; Jazan University; Community partnership.

1. INTRODUCTION

Saudi Arabia is witnessing a comprehensive renaissance as a result of what technological progress and knowledge flow impose on society, which is concerned with the connection between state-owned institutions and the partnership between them to serve the society and its members (AL-AMEER & AL-OMARI, 2020).

Society is the place in which man lives, keeps pace with its progress, coexists with its members. Its personal individuality shall not be formed and its identity shall not be formed unless this individual plays an active role in the development of society and positive participation, so the individual must participate in it society. (AL-AMIRI, 2018)

Since the educational process is the effective tool in the occurrence of any development, progress or growth. Any country interested in education and succeeds in achieving its goals, actually become among the ranks of developed countries because education is an effective tool to serve all segments and categories of society (AL-JAWAHIRI and AL-SHAMRI, 2011). Human development in the contemporary world has become the true capital for the progress of mankind, and to the extent that the nation possesses creative minds, its place is among peoples, and for the sake of creating good outcomes and powerful outcomes keeping pace with the rapid changes, community partnership has become a necessity to advance education and improve its outcomes. (KABR, 2015)

In addition, the educational process at the present time does not depend entirely on the educational institution alone, but has evolved and spread to include the family and society in all its categories and with the introduction of these new elements of the educational process, the concept of community partnership appeared. (AL-QAHTANI, 2015)

In order to enhance and advance the educational process and achieve cultural and professional development, we must increase the activation of community partnership in aspects of education, and decentralize the management of the educational process, thus achieving effective management, expanding the base of responsibility, and producing new leaders capable of making decisions (SALIM, 2005).

Since universities have expanded their mission and extended to include community service and leading the development movement in it in addition to their scientific function, they contribute to solving

problems, and also help to develop research capabilities, as they are a pillar from which the state derives its human energy capable of carrying and maintaining the burden of development (MUTAWA, 2003). The success of an educational institution in achieving its mission depends mainly on its connection and partnership with the community in which it lives. Hence, it becomes necessary for it to consolidate this partnership with its community and its surroundings taking into consideration that its success in its duties and the achievement of its mission depends mainly on the strength and durability of this relationship and partnership. (AL-AJAMI, 2000).

The first major duty of educational institutions management is to carry out effective programs to achieve successful relationships between educational institutions and society, and these programs must take into account the characteristics of the society they serve, its potentials, the extent of its ambition and aspirations, and what is expected from them, linking the community's members with the educational institution, and enlightening the individuals of society with the activities and efforts carried out by the educational institution and what it expects from them in terms of support and assistance to achieve its goals. (MORSI, 2010)

In order for the university to play its appropriate role, it must take into account the balance between what it is preparing and what the community needs, and its preparation shall be at the level and quality that the community needs (MAHMOUD, 2015). Therefore, the university must seek to activate community partnerships that can help administrators, faculty members and students to enhance their missions and provide opportunities for their participation with the community. Community partnerships with the university must be viewed as a critical tool to address urgent social problems for advancing social change by focusing university resources on real-world issues in the local community (DAVIS, 2013).

In order for the university to engage in community partnership, it must have several features, including: that community development be part of the university's mission and within perception of its objectives, that the university participates in research with institutions, that the university participates in research and development issues, and that the university motivates faculty members to participate in activities Development (AL-DALAMI and JAD, 2017). As well, the university is required to provide individuals who are able to serve the community, through knowing the requirements and needs of society. (MUSE, 2018).

The study conducted by AL-AHMAD (2015) concluded that many countries depend on partnership as a fundamental factor in achieving comprehensive development in various fields, as partnership contributes to the concerted efforts of institutions in various sectors which maximize the benefit of the institutions parties to the partnership.

Universities' tendency to communicate with the community is a good example and evidence of the influencing role for them, and that they do not work in isolation from members of society, but rather seek to engage between groups of society through social partnerships and research that have a direct impact on society, and the university's job in community partnership is not waiting to seek service. In fact, the university must, with its competencies and capabilities, go out by itself to provide service to the members of society. (MINISTRY OF HIGHER EDUCATION, 2014).

In recent years, interest has increased in the status of universities and their role in contemporary society, the future of university education and its objectives, the challenges that universities face in various social, economic, political and cultural fields, and the methods and means that universities can use to face these challenges and overcome them or overcome them and adapt them to their advantage to achieve its objectives and serve its scientific mission. (AL-MARAGHI, 2016)

Because of the role of Jazan University and its contribution to achieving development for the Saudi society, it is therefore necessary to activate the community partnership at Jazan University with various sectors in society.

Therefore, the university administration must give the community partnership great care and attention, starting with laying the proper foundations for it in planning, then organization, coordination and developing it continuously to contribute to achieving the needs of society (AL-AMEER &AL-OMARI,2020).

2. DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

In order to identify the faculty members' estimates of the reality of practicing the administrative requirements to activate the community partnership at Jazan University, the arithmetic means and standard deviations of the estimates of the study sample respondents were calculated for each of the administrative requirements and for the

requirements as a whole, then these requirements were arranged in a descending order, according to the arithmetic mean for each of them, as follows:

Table No. (4-1) the arithmetic means and standard deviations of the research sample respondents' estimates of the reality of practicing the administrative requirements to activate the community partnership at Jazan University from their viewpoint, arranged in descending order according to the arithmetic means

SN	Requirement	Number of phrases	Arithmetic mean	Standard deviation	Order (arrangement)	Degree of reality
1	Planning-related requirements	9	4.12	0.68	1	Agree
2	Organization-related requirements	8	4.01	0.78	2	Agree
3	Coordination-related requirements	10	4.00	0.76	3	Agree
General Arithmetic Mean		27	4.04	0.69	-	Agree

It is evident from Table (4-1) that the research sample respondents' estimates of the reality of practicing the administrative requirements to activate community partnership at Jazan University include three axes, which are respectively according to their arithmetic mean (planning-related requirements, organization-related requirements, and coordination-related requirements). All of them came with a response score (agree), where the arithmetic means of the axes ranged between (4.0 and 4.12), and these means fall into the fourth category of the 5-point scale categories, which indicates the degree of response (Agree).

The general arithmetic mean of the axis is (4.04 out of 5.0) with a standard deviation (0.69), and this indicates that the practice of administrative requirements to activate community partnership at Jazan University came with a degree of (Agree), where planning-related requirements come first with a general arithmetic mean (4.12) and a standard deviation (0.68), followed by organization-related requirements with an arithmetic mean (4.01) and a standard deviation (0.78), and then coordination-related requirements come among the least administrative requirements for activating community partnership at Jazan University in terms of practice with an arithmetic mean (2.4.0) and a standard deviation (0.76).

The results of the current study were also in agreement with the result of the study conducted by MUHAMMAD (2017), which

concluded that the level of activating community partnership among heads of department in private universities was at a high level, and the result of the current study agreed with the result of the study conducted by EUBANKS (2017), which concluded that the university preparedness can be improved using community partnerships.

Whereas the results of the current study differed with the result of the study conducted by DRAKE and MAYA'A (2014) &(ALQAHTANI &AYENTIMI,2020),which concluded that the estimates of faculty members showed that the level of partnership between universities and private sector institutions was medium for all areas of partnership, and the result of the current study differed with the result of the study conducted by KHATER (2015) which concluded that the Egyptian universities' implementation of the partnership is achieved at a very weak degree, as well as the result of the current study differed with the result of study conducted by MAHMOUD (2015), which concluded that the partnership between the Syrian public universities and the local community was medium, and the results of the current study also differed with the result of the study conducted by AL-HAMMAD (2017) which concluded that there is a deficiency in the partnership between universities and public education institutions in the Kingdom.

In the following, we discuss in some detail the reality of practicing administrative requirements to activate community partnership at Jazan University:

2.1. Planning-Related Administrative Requirements

Frequencies, percentages, arithmetic means, and standard deviation of the responses of the study sample respondents were calculated, and these phrases were arranged according to the arithmetic mean of each of them, and the results concluded the following:

The axis of the reality of practicing planning-related administrative requirements to activate community partnership at Jazan University includes (9) phrases, the arithmetic means of which ranged between (4.13 and 4.41), and these means fall into the two categories (fourth and fifth) of the 5-point scale categories. The

previous result indicates that the responses of the study respondents about the axis phrases range from the degree of response (agree - strongly agree).

This indicates that there is agreement among the study respondents to practice planning-related administrative requirements to activate the community partnership at Jazan University, and this may be attributed to the importance of the planning process and its role in providing a common understanding within educational institutions of the goals and achievements that the organization seeks to achieve, and the steps necessary for the implementation process as it contributes to the good and integrated planning of the community partnership process. As stated in a study MELLAHI & WOOD. (2013).

As well it includes determining the policies, rules and procedures necessary for its implementation, and this is what is emphasized by (DÖTTERWEICH, 2006), where he indicated that there are axes for building an effective community partnership represented in: A clear definition of the common vision and objectives between the parties of the partnership and the establishment of an organizational structure for the partnership, the development of cooperative work procedures while adhering to the specific role of each partner according to what has been agreed upon, in addition to continuing the implementation of partnership projects in light of political and economic changes.

2.2. Organization-Related Administrative Requirements

Frequencies, percentages, arithmetic means, and standard deviation of the responses of the study sample respondents were calculated, and these phrases were arranged according to the arithmetic mean of each of them, and the results concluded the following:

The axis of the reality of practicing organization-related administrative requirements to activate community partnership at Jazan University includes (8) phrases, the arithmetic means of which ranged between (3.77, 4.15), and these means fall into the fourth category of the 5-point scale categories, and the previous result indicates that the responses of the study respondents about the axis phrases came with a degree (Agree).

The general arithmetic mean is (4.01) with a standard deviation (0.78), and this indicates that there is agreement among the study

respondents, and this may be attributed to the important role of the organization process in effectively achieving the objectives of institutions, by defining the roles that each individual should play and the work assigned to him, and the suitability of his job to other jobs. The organization process would achieve coordination between various collective efforts, and this is what AL-SALEM & AL-DAOUD (2001), GIBSON, DAVIES (2008) and AL-RASHED (2018) emphasized, as they explained that the organization has a fundamental role in activating the process of community partnership by forming a mechanism to link the university with other community institutions, especially the institutions of production and services, and to interact with them so that they contribute to solving development problems, and to provide joint programs aimed at raising the level of community members, improving the efficiency of the workforce, and increasing production levels.

2.3. Coordination-Related Administrative Requirements

Frequencies, percentages, arithmetic means, and standard deviation of the responses of the study sample respondents were calculated, and these phrases were arranged according to the arithmetic mean of each of them, and the results concluded the following:

General arithmetic mean is (4.0) with a standard deviation (0.76), and this indicates that there is agreement among the study respondents to practice coordination-related administrative requirements to activate the community partnership at Jazan University, and this may be attributed to the important role of the coordination process in enhancing the efforts of institutions in a way that contributes to achieving common goals, as coordination contributes to achieving cooperation and balance with other institutions to achieve goals away from conflict and duplication. AL-THUBAITI (1997) explained that coordination is necessary and important to unify efforts in various departments and units inside and outside the institution to achieve the general and corporate goals, and to integrate the efforts of institutions to achieve the objectives of society.

3. RESEARCH RECOMMENDATIONS

In light of the results concluded by present study, the following recommendations can be proposed that may contribute to improving the activation of community partnership at Jazan University:

1. Establish a center or unit specialized only in managing community partnership at the university (AL-GHAMDI, 2018).
2. Give sufficient powers and authorities to those qualified to plan and implement community partnership at the university (ALLUI&SAHNI,2016)
3. Provide an appropriate budget to support the activation of community partnership at the university.
4. Reduce administrative transactions upon establishing community partnership and reducing the bodies that must be addressed. (ALQAHTANI&AYENTIMI,2020)
5. Strengthen coordination between the various departments and colleges at the university in activating community partnerships between them or between them and other institutions and universities.
6. Provide facilities in each of the university's colleges so as to active the community partnership.
7. Provide training and qualification for faculty members to activate community partnership.
8. Encourage the activation of community partnership and linking its activation with material and moral incentives (EUBANKS, 2017).
9. Spread awareness of the importance of community partnership between faculty members and students.
10. Demonstrate the administrative mechanism to activate the community partnership of institutions and faculty members.
11. Provide a guide in the university magazine that clarifies the mechanisms of the university's partnership with community institutions.
12. Conduct a periodic meeting to discuss developments and proposals to activate community partnership at the university.

Research proposals for Future Studies

In light of the results concluded, the girl-researcher proposes some suggestions that will hopefully contribute to enriching the educational field in that field:

- I. Conduct a similar study dealing with the reality of practicing the administrative requirements to activate community partnership in other universities and in other regions.
- II. Conduct a study dealing with the administrative challenges facing the activation of community partnership.
- III. Conduct a study dealing with community partnership and its role in developing education.
- IV. Conduct a study that deals with a proposed vision to activate the community partnership in universities.
- V. Conduct a study on the importance of activating community partnership at the university in light of the Kingdom's vision (2030).

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